

3. M. KELLY and G. LANG, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta*, 1970, **223**, 86.
4. G. N. SCHRAUZER and G. SCHLESINGER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **92**, 1308.
5. PALMER, "Experimental Inorganic Chemistry", Oxford University, 1954, pp. 406-408.
6. JHONSON, LOCK and WILLIAMS, *Chem. Ind. (London)*, 1963, 333; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 1054.
7. T. K. BANERJEE, Ph.D. Dissertation, Calcutta University, 1979.
8. B. C. KUNDU, Ph.D. Dissertation, Calcutta University, 1978.
9. S. SATAPATHY and B. SAHOO, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1971, **33**, 1313.

"Physicochemical Studies on the Composition and Stability of the Complexes of UO_2^{++} ion and Ag(I) with N-Glycylglycine"

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ON account of the increased significance of the amino acids in pharmaceutical, biological and industrial field, considerable interest regarding their electrochemical behaviour has been shown in the past two decades. Saxena and co-workers have made extensive study on the electrometric behaviour of some of the amino acids¹⁻². This communication reports the polarographic determination of the stability constants of the complexes of UO_2^{++} ion with N-Glycylglycine and also the determination of composition and stability constants of Ag(I) complexes of N-Glycylglycine at 30° and 40° by potentiometric and conductometric titration techniques. There is, however, no reference in the literature on the study of the present system.

Experimental

N-Glycylglycine was supplied by B.D.H. chemicals Poole England and all other chemicals used were of AnalR grade.

In case of the polarographic study of N-glycylglycine complexes with uranyl ion, the concentration of UO_2^{++} ion was 1 mM in the presence of 0.1M NaClO_4 and 0.002% Triton X-100. The concentration of ligand was varied from 0.02 to 0.13M.

Toshniwal polarograph in conjunction with a thermostated H-cell was used for recording the current voltage curves. The capillary used had the following characteristics in 0.1 M NaClO_4 : $m=2.953$ mgm/sec, $t=2.5$ sec/drop, $h=44.0$ cms and -0.4 V vs S.C.E.

pH measurements were made on a Toshniwal pH meter (Type CL-46) with a glass electrode assembly.

Conductance was measured on electronic eye type conductometer (L.B.R.; W.T.W. Germany). The temperature was controlled by a Universal thermostat (type U_3).

Results and Discussion

Polarographic Study :

The current-voltage curves of UO_2^{++} ion in presence of different concentrations of N-glycylglycine are plotted at 30°. In each case a single well defined cathodic wave appeared. All the plots of $\log(i/i_d - i)$ vs $-E_{de}$ yielded straight lines and the slopes agreed with the reversibility of the reduction. The cathodic shift in $E_{1/2}$ coupled with decrease in diffusion current on increasing N-glycylglycine concentration shows the complex formation with UO_2^{++} ion. The plot of i_d vs $\sqrt{h_{eff}}$ was found to be linear indicating the diffusion controlled nature of the reduction of UO_2^{++} complexes of N-Glycylglycine.

The curvature obtained in the plot of $-E_{1/2}$ Vs. $-\log C_x$ showed the successive complex formation and hence the method of DeFord and Hume^{3,4} was adopted for deriving various functions $F_j(X)$: From the experimental data, the complexity function $F_j(X)$ which is polynomial in (X) , is set up; the coefficients of the latter are required β_n . The graphical extrapolation reduces the polynomial equation to N-equations from which the corresponding β_n are obtained and are given below :

UO_2^{++} -N-glycylglycine complexes at 30°
 $\beta_1 = 1, \beta_2 = 280.$

Potentiometric Studies :

The stoichiometry of the reaction between Ag^+ and N-glycylglycine were determined by potentiometric titrations of mixtures of the reactions in various ratio against standard NaOH (0.1M).

Addition of an equimolar concentration of Ag^+ greatly alters the shape of the free ligand titration curve (Fig. 1) as a result of complex formation and consequently a considerable lowering in buffer region starts. The inflection at $m=1$ suggesting the formation of 1 : 1 complex. When 2 moles of ligand are added to 1 mole of Ag^+ the inflection at one mole of NaOH per mole of metal ion again indicates the formation of 1 : 1 complex.

Fig. 2 represents the change in conductivity when solutions of ligand were titrated against AgNO_3 solution. The breaks in the titration curves suggest the formation of 1 : 1 complex.

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titrations of Ag^+ in N-G.G. at ratios of N-G.G. : Ag^+ against NaOH (0.1M).

Fig. 2. Conductometric titrations of M/10 AgNO_3 against N-G.G.

KNO_3 and HClO_4 (2 mM) for initial lowering of buffer region in absence and presence of metal ion were carried out at 30° and 40° against 0.1M NaOH and the concentration of bound ligand, calculated from the horizontal distance between the corresponding curves, was divided by the metal ion concentration to obtain formation function \bar{n} . At any pH, the value of free ligand concentration (A) was calculated from the relation

$$[A] = \frac{[\text{N-GG}]_{\text{Total}} - [\text{N-GG}]_{\text{Bound}}}{[\text{H}^+]\text{K}_a + 1}$$

Here N-GG = N-glycylglycine.

where K_a is the dissociation constant of N-glycylglycine⁷ is 8.5×10^{-9} . The formation curves obtained at different temperatures by plotting \bar{n} vs. $-\log(A)$ reveal the formation of 1:1 complex. The log K values were read directly from the graph at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and found to be 8.01 and 8.055 at 30° and 40° respectively.

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References

1. R. S. SAXENA and G. L. KHANDELWAL, *Indian J. Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **15A**, 757.
2. R. S. SAXENA and M. C. SAXENA, *Monatshefte für Chemie*, 1977, **108**, 829.
3. D. D. DEFORD and D. N. HUME, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 532.
4. D. N. HUME, D. D. DEFORD and G. C. B. CAVE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5323.
5. M. CALVIN and N. C. MELCHIOR, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3270.
6. J. BJERRUM, *Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solutions*, P. Hasse & Sons, Copenhagen, 1941.
7. E. ARTHUR Martell & Robert, M. SMITH, "Critical Stability Constants", Vol. I, Aminoacids, Plenum Press (New York & England).

Ti(IV), Zr(IV), Hf(IV), Th(IV), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) Complexes of Vanillideneanthranilic Acid and Vanillidenebromoanthranilic Acid

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Calvin and Melchior's extension⁵ of Bjerrum's method⁶ has been employed for the determination of stability constants of the complexes. The pH titrations of N-glycylglycine at ionic strength 0.1M

METAL chelates of the Schiff bases have been recently reviewed by Holm *et al.*¹. Copper acetylacetonanthranilic acid², copper N-(2-hydroxy-1 naphthalidene) anthranilic acid³,